

DISTOLATERAL SUBUNGUAL ONYCHOMYCOSIS IN CHILDREN SUCCESSFULLY TREATED WITH TOPICAL 2% KETOCONAZOLE LOTION

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ABSTRACT Onychomycosis is a chronic fungal infection caused by dermatophytes or yeasts which lead to the destruction of the nail plate of the hands and feet. Onychomycosis is rare in children, but its prevalence is reported to increase in children and adolescents, accounting for 20% of all dermatophyte infections. Distolateral subungual onychomycosis (DLSO) is the most common clinical form. Treatment of onychomycosis depends on several factors including the severity of the nail, the efficacy and potential side effects of the treatment regimen — usual onychomycosis in children treated with a combination of systemic and topical therapy. And usually, a patient treated with topical therapies alone don't give a satisfactory result.

We report a case of Distolateral Subungual Onychomycosis in an 11-year-old girl with nail dystrophy on the hand and foot in the last three months. Physical examination showed found discolouration and subungual keratosis on the third fingernail and the third and four toenails. Fungal culture from the toenail and fingernail scraping showed the growth of *T. rubrum* and *T. schoenleinii*, respectively. Based on the history taking, physical examination, and supporting examination, a diagnosis of onychomycosis was made. The patient responded well to a topical application of 2% Ketoconazole lotion after 20 days.

KEYWORDS Children, Distolateral Subungual Onychomycosis, Ketoconazole lotion

Introduction

Onychomycosis is a chronic disease caused by dermatophytes, yeasts and fungi, which destroys the nails of the hands and feet. Onychomycosis is rare in children, where an incidence of only 0.3-0.44%. However, the prevalence increases in adolescents and adults, where the value reaches 20% of all dermatophyte infections.[1],[2]

The main predisposing factors for fungal infections of the nail in children are trauma and hyperhidrosis that usually appear after puberty. Systemic diseases such as diabetes and psoriasis as well as congenital syndromes such as primary and secondary immunodeficiency and Down Syndrome also play a role in the development of onychomycosis in children. Besides the use of socks and shoes that are infected from other family members, poor personal hygiene, nail-biting habits and exercise also increase the risk of onychomycosis. This can be explained by the presence of chronic nail plate in athletes, especially soccer players and swimmers.[3],[4]

The most common causative agents for onychomycosis are dermatophytes and *Candida* species. In most cases, onychomycosis is caused by dermatophytes, *T. rubrum* and *T. Interdigitale* are accounted for 90% of cases, and *T. tonsurans* and *E. floccosum* cause others. Nondermatophytic yeasts and fungi such as *Acremonium*, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Scopulariopsis brevicaulis*, and *Scytalidium* accounted for 10% of toenail onychomycosis.

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Figure 1: Before treatment (a,b) dystrophic nail, discolouration, subungual keratosis and crust at the 3rd right fingernail. (c,d) dystrophic nail, discolouration, subungual keratosis and pus at 3rd & 4th right toenail.

[1],[2],[5]

Onychomycosis is a fungal infection caused by various pathogens which can adopt any of several clinical patterns. The three main clinical patterns are distolateral subungual onychomycosis (DLSO), proximal subungual onychomycosis (PSO), and white superficial onychomycosis (WSO). [1],[6]

Investigations to confirm the diagnosis before treatment with oral antifungals are recommended to avoid unnecessary treatment. Direct microscopy examination using potassium hydroxide to find hyphae from subungual debris is advice although the results are often negative. Also, although hyphae are found, the results of the fungal culture can be negative. Culture is the most specific test for onychomycosis — samples were taken from the nail plate accompanied by debris and cultured in Saboroud Dextrose Agar (with and without antimicrobials). Periodic Acid-Schiff staining of nail pieces is the most sensitive test.[7]

Management of onychomycosis depends on several factors including the severity of the infection and concomitant tinea pedis infection. At present, there is no FDA-approved drug for onychomycosis in the pediatric age group. Although there are no clinical trials that show the success of topical antifungal therapy in children, initial therapy with topical antifungals may be successful due to a faster nail growth rate.[1],[3]

Here we report a case of onychomycosis in an 11-year-old girl with a history of dystrophic nail since three months before admission which showed a good clinical improvement in approximately 20 days after being treated with 2% ketoconazole lotion.

Case Report

An 11-year-old girl presented with a dark yellow and dystrophic nail at the right fingernail and toenails since three months ago. It started from the distal nail and spread to proximal nail. Two weeks before admission, pus was noticed to appear on the skin near to the proximal toenail — no history of pets and family with the same complaint. The patient was a student who wore occlusive footwear every day for many hours. Physical examination showed found discolouration and subungual keratosis on the third fingernail and the third and four toenails.

The results of complete blood count and liver and renal function were all in normal limits. Nail clipping was negative for hyphae on potassium hydroxide examination. The fungal culture showed *T. rubrum* species at toenail and *T. schoenleinii* at a fingernail.

Fig.1.a.

Fig.1.b.

Figure 2: Fungal culture (a) *T.schoenleinii* colony, a yellow-white colony with radial grooves (b) yellow colony was shown on the back side (c) *T.rubrum* colony, a picture of the white colony with a velvety smooth surface (d) red colony was shown on the back side

Fig.1.c.

Fig.2.a.

Fig.1.d.

Fig.2.b.

Fig.2.c.

Fig.2.d.

Fig.3.a. Lactophenol Cotton Blue stain (a) *T.schoenleinii*, clear hyphae without septae with broadened hyphae tips (nail-heads).

Fig.3.b. Numerous chlamydospores are present (b) *T.rubrum*, clear hyphae without septae with water droplet of microconidia on several hyphae, no macronidia images.

Fig.4.a.

Fig.4.b.

Figure 4: (a,b) 20 days after treatment showed good clinical improvement, but the nail dystrophy was still apparent (c,d) 43 days after treatment - significant improvement was seen, and the nail dystrophy had already improved.

The patient has prescribed ketoconazole 2% lotion daily. On the 20th day of treatment, the subungual keratosis on the fingernails and toenail already disappeared, with only limited improvement on nail dystrophy. In the 43rd day, the dystrophic nails had already fully recovered.

Discussion

Onychomycosis in children is rare, but the prevalence is increasing in children and adolescents, where the value reaches 20% of all dermatophyte infections diagnosed in children. It is hypothesized that children, especially infant, are less likely to suffer from onychomycosis because of the rapid nail growth, smaller nail surface area, low risk of nail trauma, and less exposure to pathogenic environment. [1],[2]

DLSO is the most common presentation of dermatophyte nail infection. Toenails are more commonly affected than fingernails. The fungus invades the nail and nail bed by penetrating the distal or lateral margins. The affected nail becomes thickened and discolored with a varying degree of onycholysis (separation of the nail plate from the nail bed), although the nail plate is not initially affected. The infection may be confined to one side of the nail or involve the entire nail bed. Eventually the nail plate becomes friable and may break up. The most common causative organism is *T. rubrum*. As DLSO caused by dermatophytes or nondermatophytes both has a similar clinical presentation, it is

Fig.4.c.

Fig.4.d.

important to obtain a nail sample for mycological examination to confirm the causative organism. Tinea unguium of the toenails usually occurs secondary to tinea pedis, while fingernail infection often follows tinea manuum, tinea capitis or tinea corporis. Tinea unguium may involve a single nail, more than one nail, both fingernails and toenails, or, in exceptional circumstances, all of them. The clinical signs of tinea unguium are often difficult to distinguish from those of several other infectious causes of nail damage, such as Candida, mould or bacterial infection. Unlike dermatophytosis, nail candidiasis usually begins in the proximal nail plate accompanied by paonychia. Bacterial infection, particularly due to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, tends to result in green or black discoloration of the nails. Sometimes bacterial infection can coexist with fungal infection and may require treatment. [6]

Many noninfectious conditions can produce nail changes that mimic onychomycosis. Nonfungal causes of nail dystrophies include chronic trauma, psoriasis, onycholysis, subungual malignant melanoma and lichen planus. Because of that, confirmation of a clinical diagnosis of onychomycosis should be obtained before starting treatment. This is important for several reasons: to eliminate nonfungal dermatological conditions from the diagnosis; to detect mixed infections; and to diagnose patients with less responsive forms of onychomycosis, such as toenail infections due to *T. rubrum*. Good nail specimens are difficult to obtain but are crucial for maximizing laboratory diagnosis. Material should be taken from any discoloured, dystrophic or brittle parts of the nail. The affected nail should be cut as far back as possible through the entire thickness and should include any crumbly material. Nail drills, scalpels and nail elevators may be helpful but must be sterilized between patients. If associated skin lesions are present, samples from these are likely to be infected with the same organism and are more likely to give a positive culture. Traditionally, laboratory detection and identification of dermatophytes consists of culture and microscopy, which yields results within approximately 2–6 weeks.[6]

KOH (Potassium Hydroxide) examination was performed to find hyphae in nail scrapings, but in patients there were no

hyphae. Some literature states that KOH examination is often negative even when clinical suspicion is high, and nails with hyphae on KOH examination, culture results can be negative.[1]

Fungal culture using SDA from the toe and finger nail after 14 days showed fungal growth. Based on macroscopic and microscopic examination of hand nails, *Trichophyton schoenleinii* species were found, whereas in the toenails *Trichophyton rubrum* species were found which infect the patient's toenails. In accordance with the literature which states that culture is the most specific test for onychomycosis. Where in most cases, onychomycosis is caused by *T. rubrum* and *T. Interdigitale*. Although rarely *T. schoenleinii* is also one of the causes of onychomycosis.[8],[9]

Laboratory examination is routinely carried out before starting therapy. In this case, all results were in normal limit. This is related to the selection of antifungal drugs, where the potential for side effects such as hepatotoxic, kidney function disorders and blood disorders must take into account before making the choice for an antifungal agent.[1]

Treatment of onychomycosis is challenging and recurrence is common. Therefore, treatment using systemic antifungal medication for a longer period is commonly required. However, doctor and parents are often hesitant to treat children with systemic drug that requires laboratory monitoring and could cause systemic toxicities.[10]

The hard keratin and compact structure of the dorsal nail plate act as a barrier to topical drug diffusion into and through the nail plate. The concentration of topically applied drug can decrease by 1000 times from the outer to inner surface. The hydrophilic nature of the nail plate also precludes absorption of most lipophilic molecules with high molecular weights. The role of monotherapy with topical antifungals is limited to SWO (except in transverse or striate infections), early DLSO (except in the presence of longitudinal streaks) when < 80% of the nail plate is affected with lack of involvement of the lunula, or when systemic antifungals are contraindicated.[6]

As we know treatment using systemic antifungal is believed to be more effective than topical preparation in treating onychomycosis in children. Among the different antifungal therapies for children systemic therapy itraconazole has the highest clinical cure rate (94%) Topical therapy using ciclopirox show a 70% clinical cure rate. At present, there are no Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved drugs for the treatment of onychomycosis in children. In development country such as in our case, treatment using systemic therapy is also very expensive and associated with greater risk of side effects. Therefore, before we make a treatment choice we should understand the adverse effects associated with antifungal medication. The preferred antifungal agent and widely used for the treatment of onychomycosis is terbinafine and itraconazole.

Topical treatment could minimize drug interactions, acute liver injury, and systemic toxicity. Thus, using topical antifungal agents in children seem to be prudent, although the cure rate is inferior to systemic agents. Besides that, compliance for treatment using topical treatment in children is higher. That's why topical treatments are more beneficial, because they have minimal systemic absorption rates, and therefore fewer side effects. Moreover, children are more responsive to topical therapy because they have thinner and faster-growing nails. [11] Ciclopirox is the most commonly used topical agent despite the high cost. Although there are no clinical trials that show the efficacy of topical antifungals in children, initial therapy with

topical antifungals may prove successful because the rate of nail growth is faster in children. This reason became the basis of using 2% ketoconazole lotion in this case.

Ketoconazole is an imidazole that demonstrates good efficacy for onychomycosis but with a high risk of hepatotoxicity, especially with long-term therapy. In the U.S.A. and Europe, including the U.K., it has been removed from the market for the treatment of superficial mycoses.[6] Topical preparation has been shown to be a safe and effective treatment in treating dermatophytes.[12]

The use of topical drugs is limited in the case of onychomycosis which only affects half the distal nail plate or under conditions that cannot tolerate systemic drug administration. Combination therapy regimens may have a higher cure rate than oral or topical therapy alone. Other adjuvant therapies for onychomycosis such as nail surgery and laser (Nd: Yag / CO₂). [1,3,13,14] Children with onychomycosis must be evaluated for infections that occur together with tinea pedis and capitis. All close family members must also be examined.

Conclusion

Topical therapy is an option to treat onychomycosis with lower costs, drug interactions, side effects and complications. Also, its ease of use will increase patient compliance. This case shows that monotherapy ketoconazole lotion resulted in excellent clinical improvement and reduced the risk of side effect from using systemic treatment.

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